

R code and output for “Improved two-step analysis of germination data from complex experimental designs”

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Preparations

Information about R version

```
sessionInfo()
```

```
## R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)
## Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
## Running under: Ubuntu 18.04.5 LTS
##
## Matrix products: default
## BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/blas/libblas.so.3.7.1
## LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/lapack/liblapack.so.3.7.1
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_CTYPE=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_NUMERIC=C
## [3] LC_TIME=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_COLLATE=da_DK.UTF-8
## [5] LC_MONETARY=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_MESSAGES=da_DK.UTF-8
## [7] LC_PAPER=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_NAME=C
## [9] LC_ADDRESS=C LC_TELEPHONE=C
## [11] LC_MEASUREMENT=da_DK.UTF-8 LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods base
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] compiler_4.0.3 magrittr_2.0.1 tools_4.0.3 htmltools_0.5.0
## [5] yaml_2.2.1 stringi_1.5.3 rmarkdown_2.5 knitr_1.30
## [9] stringr_1.4.0 xfun_0.19 digest_0.6.27 rlang_0.4.9
## [13] evaluate_0.14
```

Loading relevant packages

```
library(car)
library(dplyr)
library(ggplot2)
library(magic)
library(metafor)
library(multcomp)
```

```

library(plyr)

library(devtools)
install_github("DoseResponse/drc")
install_github("DoseResponse/drcData")
library(drcData)
library(drc)

```

Defining helper functions for Step 1

```

paramToWide <- function(allFits, tVal = NULL)
{
  mpNames <- c("b", "d", "e")
  numPar <- length(mpNames)
  numTval <- length(tVal)

  perFit <- function(fitObj)
  {
    if (is.null(fitObj)) {return(c(rep(NA, 2 * (numPar + numTval)), 0))}

    tempNames <- fitObj[["fct"]][["names"]]
    numPar2 <- length(tempNames)
    tempNames2 <- paste(tempNames, ":(Intercept)", sep = "")

    returnMat <- matrix(NA, numPar + numTval, 2)
    rmNames <- mpNames
    if (!is.null(tVal)) {rmNames <- c(rmNames, paste("t:", tVal, sep = ""))}
    rownames(returnMat) <- rmNames
    coefSum <- coef(summary(fitObj))
    for (i in 1:numPar2)
    {
      returnMat[tempNames[i], 1:2] <- coefSum[tempNames2[i], 1:2]
    }
    if (numTval > 0) {for (i in 1:numTval)
    {
      returnMat[i + numPar, 1:2] <- ED(fitObj, tVal[i], display = FALSE)[1:2]
    }}

    returnVec <- c(as.vector(t(returnMat)), numPar2)

    names0 <- paste(rep(mpNames, rep(2, numPar)), rep(c(".est", ".se"), numPar), sep = "")

    tvNames <- paste("t", tVal, sep = "")
    if (numTval > 0) {names0 <- c(names0,
                                paste(rep(tvNames, rep(2, numTval)),
                                      rep(c(".est", ".se"), numTval), sep = ""))}
    names(returnVec) <- c(names0, "npar")

    returnVec
  }
}

ldply(allFits, perFit)

```

```

}

paramToLong <- function(allFits, groupVars, parmsWide)
{
  mpNames <- c("b", "d", "e")

  longData0 <- parmsWide

  longData <- longData0[rep(row.names(longData0), longData0[["npar"]]), ]

  coefListN <- lapply(allFits, function(modelFit) {if (!is.null(modelFit))
    {names(coef(modelFit))} else {NULL}})
  coefListN2 <- compact(coefListN) # removing NULL elements
  coefVecN <- do.call("c", coefListN2)
  longData[["Parm"]] <- as.factor(coefVecN)
  levels(longData[["Parm"]]) <- mpNames

  coefList <- lapply(allFits, function(modelFit) {if (!is.null(modelFit))
    {coef(modelFit)} else {NULL}})
  coefList2 <- compact(coefList) # removing NULL elements
  coefVec <- as.numeric(do.call("c", coefList2))

  vcovList <- lapply(allFits, function(modelFit) {if (!is.null(modelFit))
    {vcov(modelFit)} else {NULL}})
  vcovList2 <- compact(vcovList) # removing NULL elements
  vcMat <- do.call("adiag", vcovList2)

  return(list(data = data.frame(longData, Resp = coefVec),
             vcovMat = vcMat))
}

updateStep1Data <- function(allFits, groupVars, tVal = NULL)
{
  parmsWide <- paramToWide(allFits, tVal)
  parmsLong <- paramToLong(allFits, groupVars, parmsWide)

  return(list(fits = allFits, wide = parmsWide, long = parmsLong))
}

makeStep1Data <- function(GerVar, StartVar, EndVar, drmFct, fullData, groupVars,
                          tVal = NULL, plotFit = FALSE)
{
  fitFct <- function(dataSet)
  {
    modelFit <- try(drm(as.formula(paste(GerVar, "~", StartVar, "+", EndVar)),
                      data = dataSet,
                      fct = drmFct,
                      type = "event"), silent = TRUE)

    if (inherits(modelFit, "try-error")) {modelFit <- NULL}
  }
}

```

```

    if (plotFit & !is.null(modelFit)) {plot(modelFit)}

    return(modelFit)
  }

allFits <- dplyr::full_data(fullData, groupVars, fitFct)

updateStep1Data(allFits, groupVars) # after input from Omer Kapiluto
}

```

Defining helper functions for plotting after Step 2

```

makeRawData <- function(subSet, subexVar, startVar, gerVar)
{
  #tempD <- subset(dataSet, Treat == "GA3.0")

  obsMat <- ddply(subSet, subexVar,
                 function(x) data.frame(Time = x[[startVar]],
                                         Ger = head(c(0, cumsum(x[[gerVar]]/sum(x[[gerVar]])), -1)))

  retMat <- ddply(obsMat[order(obsMat[, 2]), ], "Time", function(x){mean(x[["Ger"]])})
  colnames(retMat) <- c("Time", "Germinated")
  return(retMat)
}

makePlotData <- function(modelFit, groupLevel, timeRan) # works only for LL.2() and LL.3() models
{
  coefVec <- coef(summary(modelFit))[, 1]
  selInd <- regexr(groupLevel, row.names(coef(summary(modelFit)))) > 0
  coef1 <- coefVec[selInd]
  lenCoef <- length(coef1)
  parNames <- c("b", "d", "e")
  names(coef1) <- parNames[1:lenCoef]
  if (lenCoef<3) {names(coef1) <- parNames[c(1, 3)]} else {names(coef1) <- parNames}
  vcMat1 <- vcov(modelFit)[selInd, selInd]

  # Generating fitted values and corresponding 95% confidence intervals
  # (based on a grid on size 100)
  timeVec <- seq(timeRan[1], timeRan[2], length.out = 100)
  resultsMat <- matrix(NA, 100, 5)

  if (lenCoef<3) {denomPart <- "1/(1+("} else {denomPart <- "d/(1+("}
  for (i in 1:100)
  {
    resultsMat[i, ] <-
      c(timeVec[i], as.vector(unlist(deltaMethod(coef1, paste(denomPart,
                                                             timeVec[i],
                                                             "/e^b)", vcMat1))))
  }
  colnames(resultsMat) <- c("Time", "Fitted", "SE", "LCI", "UCI")
  resultsMat <- as.data.frame(resultsMat)
}

```

```

return(resultsMat)
}

```

Example 1

Preparations

```
head(Eryngium.sparganophyllum0)
```

```
##   Day Treat Type Rep Germ
## 1   2 GA3-0  GA3   1   0
## 2   4 GA3-0  GA3   1   0
## 3   7 GA3-0  GA3   1   0
## 4   9 GA3-0  GA3   1   1
## 5  11 GA3-0  GA3   1   1
## 6  14 GA3-0  GA3   1   0
```

```
Eryngium.sparganophyllum1 <- Eryngium.sparganophyllum0
Eryngium.sparganophyllum1[["Rep"]] <- with(Eryngium.sparganophyllum1,
interaction(Type, Treat, Rep))
```

```
table(Eryngium.sparganophyllum1[["Rep"]])
```

```
##
##   GA3.Cold-10.1  Temp.Cold-10.1  GA3.Cold-12.1  Temp.Cold-12.1  GA3.Cold-14.1
##              0              14              0              14              0
##   Temp.Cold-14.1  GA3.Cold-16.1  Temp.Cold-16.1  GA3.Cold-18.1  Temp.Cold-18.1
##              14              0              14              0              14
##   GA3.Cold-2.1   Temp.Cold-2.1   GA3.Cold-4.1   Temp.Cold-4.1   GA3.Cold-6.1
##              0              13              0              13              0
##   Temp.Cold-6.1  GA3.Cold-8.1   Temp.Cold-8.1  GA3.Control.1  Temp.Control.1
##              13              0              14              0              13
##   GA3.GA3-0.1    Temp.GA3-0.1   GA3.GA3-1000.1  Temp.GA3-1000.1  GA3.GA3-250.1
##              13              0              13              0              13
##   Temp.GA3-250.1  GA3.GA3-500.1  Temp.GA3-500.1  GA3.GA3-750.1  Temp.GA3-750.1
##              0              13              0              13              0
##   GA3.Cold-10.2  Temp.Cold-10.2  GA3.Cold-12.2  Temp.Cold-12.2  GA3.Cold-14.2
##              0              13              0              13              0
##   Temp.Cold-14.2  GA3.Cold-16.2  Temp.Cold-16.2  GA3.Cold-18.2  Temp.Cold-18.2
##              13              0              13              0              13
##   GA3.Cold-2.2   Temp.Cold-2.2   GA3.Cold-4.2   Temp.Cold-4.2   GA3.Cold-6.2
##              0              12              0              12              0
##   Temp.Cold-6.2  GA3.Cold-8.2   Temp.Cold-8.2  GA3.Control.2  Temp.Control.2
##              12              0              13              0              12
##   GA3.GA3-0.2    Temp.GA3-0.2   GA3.GA3-1000.2  Temp.GA3-1000.2  GA3.GA3-250.2
##              13              0              13              0              13
##   Temp.GA3-250.2  GA3.GA3-500.2  Temp.GA3-500.2  GA3.GA3-750.2  Temp.GA3-750.2
##              0              13              0              13              0
##   GA3.Cold-10.3  Temp.Cold-10.3  GA3.Cold-12.3  Temp.Cold-12.3  GA3.Cold-14.3
##              0              13              0              13              0
##   Temp.Cold-14.3  GA3.Cold-16.3  Temp.Cold-16.3  GA3.Cold-18.3  Temp.Cold-18.3
##              13              0              13              0              13
##   GA3.Cold-2.3   Temp.Cold-2.3   GA3.Cold-4.3   Temp.Cold-4.3   GA3.Cold-6.3
##              0              12              0              12              0
```

```
## Temp.Cold-6.3    GA3.Cold-8.3    Temp.Cold-8.3    GA3.Control.3    Temp.Control.3
##              12              0              13              0              12
## GA3.GA3-0.3    Temp.GA3-0.3    GA3.GA3-1000.3    Temp.GA3-1000.3    GA3.GA3-250.3
##              13              0              13              0              13
## Temp.GA3-250.3    GA3.GA3-500.3    Temp.GA3-500.3    GA3.GA3-750.3    Temp.GA3-750.3
##              0              13              0              13              0
```

```
levels(Eryngium.sparganophyllum1[["Treat"]]) <-
  c("Cold.10", "Cold.12", "Cold.14", "Cold.16", "Cold.18",
    "Cold.2", "Cold.4", "Cold.6", "Cold.8", "Control", "GA3.0",
    "GA3.1000", "GA3.250", "GA3.500", "GA3.750")
# removing the minus in the names
```

Defining helper function for dataset conversion:

```
rearrFct <- function(dataSet, timeVar, germVar, totalseed)
{
  dataSet2 <- dataSet[c(1, 1:nrow(dataSet)), ]
  dataSet2[["Start"]] <- c(0, dataSet[["timeVar"]])
  dataSet2[["End"]] <- c(dataSet[["timeVar"]], Inf)
  dataSet2[["Germinated"]] <- c(dataSet[["germVar"], totalseed - sum(dataSet[["germVar"]])])
  dataSet2
}
```

```
Eryngium.sparganophyllum2 <- ddply(Eryngium.sparganophyllum1, c("Type", "Treat", "Rep"),
  rearrFct, timeVar = "Day", germVar = "Germ", totalseed = 16)
```

```
head(Eryngium.sparganophyllum2)
```

```
## Day Treat Type Rep Germ Start End Germinated
## 1 2 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 0 0 2 0
## 2 2 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 0 2 4 0
## 3 4 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 0 4 7 0
## 4 7 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 0 7 9 1
## 5 9 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 1 9 11 1
## 6 11 GA3.0 GA3 GA3.GA3-0.1 1 11 14 0
```

```
## Subset only the ga3 experiment
eryngium.ga <- droplevels(subset(Eryngium.sparganophyllum2, Type == "GA3"))
```

The above lines show how to convert a typical dataset into the format required for fitting event-time models. Alternatively, the dataset named *Eryngium.sparganophyllum* (without 0 at the end) in the package *drcData* can be used directly as it already has the right format.

Step 1

```
eryngium.ga.step1 <- makeStep1Data("Germinated", "Start", "End",
  LL.3(), eryngium.ga,
  c("Treat", "Rep"), plotFit = TRUE)
```


Judged from the figures all model fits seem okay.

Looking at the parameter estimates in the wide format:

```
eryngium.ga.step1[["wide"]]
```

##	Treat	Rep	b.est	b.se	d.est	d.se	e.est
## 1	GA3.0	GA3.GA3-0.1	-4.597508	2.055608	0.2546731	0.11070064	12.62563
## 2	GA3.0	GA3.GA3-0.2	-6.807917	2.414716	0.4401800	0.12487684	14.17842
## 3	GA3.0	GA3.GA3-0.3	-8.810605	3.478070	0.3125906	0.11591175	11.91195
## 4	GA3.1000	GA3.GA3-1000.1	-4.798934	1.201762	0.9528091	0.06427286	12.72819
## 5	GA3.1000	GA3.GA3-1000.2	-9.985537	2.786439	0.6874289	0.11589887	10.48493
## 6	GA3.1000	GA3.GA3-1000.3	-7.914481	2.051250	0.7514260	0.10848617	13.59621
## 7	GA3.250	GA3.GA3-250.1	-7.250069	2.217354	0.5015794	0.12542767	13.55911
## 8	GA3.250	GA3.GA3-250.2	-10.805218	3.196611	0.6250121	0.12103436	11.36903
## 9	GA3.250	GA3.GA3-250.3	-8.072240	2.192652	0.7502910	0.10829198	11.29278
## 10	GA3.500	GA3.GA3-500.1	-9.356865	3.203309	0.4375318	0.12402839	10.84489
## 11	GA3.500	GA3.GA3-500.2	-7.596792	2.567412	0.4382707	0.12424808	13.00581
## 12	GA3.500	GA3.GA3-500.3	-8.848906	2.508013	0.6251545	0.12106587	11.86218
## 13	GA3.750	GA3.GA3-750.1	-49.400418	227.953121	0.6250081	0.12102923	11.09068
## 14	GA3.750	GA3.GA3-750.2	-8.674272	2.063107	0.8755459	0.08273454	12.81769
## 15	GA3.750	GA3.GA3-750.3	-7.198555	2.319599	0.5015543	0.12542509	13.45226
##	e.se	npar					
## 1	2.5667940	3					
## 2	1.3955516	3					
## 3	1.1351922	3					
## 4	1.2599613	3					
## 5	0.5903775	3					
## 6	0.9099341	3					
## 7	1.2145813	3					
## 8	0.6337380	3					
## 9	0.6977523	3					
## 10	0.8155549	3					
## 11	1.1856684	3					

```
## 12 0.7852151    3
## 13 0.4445860    3
## 14 0.7329841    3
## 15 1.1932757    3
```

As there are no missing values for any parameter estimates the above automatic estimation worked for all 12 Petri dishes

Extracting data for Step 2 (in the long format)

```
eryngium.ga.long <- eryngium.ga.step1[["long"]]
eryngium.ga.long.data <- eryngium.ga.long[["data"]]
```

Step 2

Fitting the linear mixed model:

```
eryngium.ga.long.data[["TreatParm"]] <-
  with(eryngium.ga.long.data, interaction(Treat, Parm))

eryngium.ga.meta1 <- rma.mv(Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]],
  mods = ~ TreatParm-1,
  random = list(~Parm|Rep),
  data = eryngium.ga.long.data,
  struct = "UN")
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm - :
## Ratio of largest to smallest sampling variance extremely large. May not be able
## to obtain stable results.
```

```
summary(eryngium.ga.meta1)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 45; method: REML)
##
##   logLik Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -36.8155  73.6311  115.6311  145.0562  231.1311
##
## Variance Components:
##
## outer factor: Rep (nlvls = 15)
## inner factor: Parm (nlvls = 3)
##
##           estim  sqrt  k.lvl  fixed  level
## tau^2.1  1.2463  1.1164   15    no    b
## tau^2.2  0.0087  0.0935   15    no    d
## tau^2.3  0.9808  0.9903   15    no    e
##
##      rho.b  rho.d  rho.e    b  d  e
## b         1  0.5772  0.9588   - no no
## d  0.5772    1  0.3214   15  - no
## e  0.9588  0.3214    1   15 15  -
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
```

```

## QE(df = 30) = 47.1409, p-val = 0.0241
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 1:15):
## QM(df = 15) = 1975.9787, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## TreatParmGA3.0.b      -6.1055  1.5738  -3.8794  0.0001   -9.1902   -3.0209 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.b   -6.7579  1.1655  -5.7981 <.0001   -9.0424  -4.4735 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.b    -8.2370  1.5437  -5.3359 <.0001  -11.2626  -5.2115 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.b    -8.5615  1.6933  -5.0563 <.0001  -11.8802  -5.2428 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.b    -8.5900  1.6824  -5.1058 <.0001  -11.8874  -5.2925 ***
## TreatParmGA3.0.d       0.3294  0.0864   3.8120  0.0001    0.1600   0.4987 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.d    0.8156  0.0758  10.7578 <.0001    0.6670   0.9642 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.d     0.6337  0.0869   7.2946 <.0001    0.4634   0.8039 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.d     0.5015  0.0892   5.6201 <.0001    0.3266   0.6764 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.d     0.6999  0.0822   8.5175 <.0001    0.5389   0.8610 ***
## TreatParmGA3.0.e      12.9374  1.0393  12.4480 <.0001   10.9004  14.9744 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.e   12.0749  0.7661  15.7605 <.0001   10.5732  13.5765 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.e    11.8363  0.7376  16.0472 <.0001   10.3906  13.2819 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.e    11.7853  0.7752  15.2032 <.0001   10.2659  13.3046 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.e    12.1604  0.6918  17.5772 <.0001   10.8044  13.5163 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Fitting the linear mixed model assuming uncorrelated parameter estimates:

```

eryngium.ga.meta1x <- rma.mv(Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]],
  mods = ~ TreatParm-1,
  random = list(~Parm|Rep),
  data = eryngium.ga.long.data,
  struct = "DIAG")

```

```

## Warning in rma.mv(Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm - :
## Ratio of largest to smallest sampling variance extremely large. May not be able
## to obtain stable results.

```

```
summary(eryngium.ga.meta1x)
```

```

##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 45; method: REML)
##
##   logLik Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -37.4356  74.8713  110.8713  136.0928  173.0531
##
## Variance Components:
##
## outer factor: Rep (nlvls = 15)
## inner factor: Parm (nlvls = 3)
##
##           estim      sqrt  k.lvl  fixed  level
## tau^2.1    0.0000  0.0000    15    no    b
## tau^2.2    0.0088  0.0940    15    no    d
## tau^2.3    0.9758  0.9878    15    no    e

```

```

##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 30) = 47.1409, p-val = 0.0241
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 1:15):
## QM(df = 15) = 1655.1727, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## TreatParmGA3.0.b      -6.0051  1.4245  -4.2156 <.0001  -8.7970  -3.2132 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.b   -6.2691  0.9618  -6.5179 <.0001  -8.1543  -4.3840 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.b    -8.1649  1.3990  -5.8362 <.0001 -10.9069  -5.4229 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.b    -8.4688  1.5642  -5.4142 <.0001 -11.5346  -5.4031 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.b    -8.0110  1.5412  -5.1979 <.0001 -11.0317  -4.9903 ***
## TreatParmGA3.0.d       0.3294  0.0866   3.8043  0.0001   0.1597   0.4991 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.d    0.8170  0.0764  10.6963 <.0001   0.6673   0.9667 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.d     0.6325  0.0871   7.2659 <.0001   0.4619   0.8031 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.d     0.5014  0.0894   5.6077 <.0001   0.3261   0.6766 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.d     0.6991  0.0824   8.4797 <.0001   0.5375   0.8607 ***
## TreatParmGA3.0.e     12.8753  1.0432  12.3425 <.0001  10.8307  14.9198 ***
## TreatParmGA3.1000.e   11.9321  0.7660  15.5766 <.0001  10.4307  13.4334 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.e    11.8483  0.7408  15.9936 <.0001  10.3963  13.3002 ***
## TreatParmGA3.500.e    11.7896  0.7763  15.1874 <.0001  10.2681  13.3111 ***
## TreatParmGA3.750.e    12.1549  0.6932  17.5353 <.0001  10.7963  13.5135 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

Graphical model checking

```

plot(fitted(eryngium.ga.metal), residuals(eryngium.ga.metal, type = "rstandard")) # residual plot

```



```
qqnorm(residuals(eryngium.ga.meta1, type = "rstandard")) # QQ plot
```

Normal Q-Q Plot

Comparison of treatment combinations

Comparisons for the parameter b:

```
eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.b <-  
  c("TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.250.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b = 0",  
    "TreatParmGA3.750.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b = 0")  
  
eryngium.ga.pairwise.b <- glht(eryngium.ga.meta1,  
                               linfct = eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.b)  
  
summary(eryngium.ga.pairwise.b, test = adjusted("none"))  
  
##  
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses  
##  
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -  
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)  
##  
## Linear Hypotheses:  
##  
## Estimate Std. Error z value  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.250.b == 0 2.13151 2.20453 0.967  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 2.45599 2.31172 1.062  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 2.48444 2.30379 1.078  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.65240 1.95843 0.333  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 0.32447 2.29131 0.142  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.35293 2.28330 0.155  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.47911 1.93429 -0.765  
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.02846 2.38696 0.012  
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.80359 2.05563 -0.877  
## TreatParmGA3.750.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.83204 2.04670 -0.895  
## Pr(>|z|)  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.250.b == 0 0.334  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 0.288  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.281  
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.739  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 0.887  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.877  
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.444  
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.990  
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.380  
## TreatParmGA3.750.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.371  
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)  
confint(eryngium.ga.pairwise.b, calpha = 1.96)  
  
##
```

```

## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr upr
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.250.b == 0 2.13151 -2.18937 6.45239
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 2.45599 -2.07500 6.98697
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 2.48444 -2.03099 6.99987
## TreatParmGA3.0.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 0.65240 -3.18613 4.49093
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.500.b == 0 0.32447 -4.16649 4.81544
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.35293 -4.12234 4.82821
## TreatParmGA3.250.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.47911 -5.27032 2.31210
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.750.b == 0 0.02846 -4.64999 4.70691
## TreatParmGA3.500.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.80359 -5.83261 2.22544
## TreatParmGA3.750.b - TreatParmGA3.1000.b == 0 -1.83204 -5.84357 2.17949

```

Comparisons for the parameter d:

```

eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.d <-
  c("TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.250.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.750.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d = 0")

eryngium.ga.pairwise.d <- glht(eryngium.ga.meta1,
                              linfct = eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.d)

summary(eryngium.ga.pairwise.d, test = adjusted("none"))

```

```

##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.250.d == 0 -0.30430 0.12252 -2.484
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0 -0.17215 0.12421 -1.386
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0 -0.37057 0.11924 -3.108
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.48627 0.11495 -4.230
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0 0.13214 0.12454 1.061
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0 -0.06627 0.11958 -0.554

```

```

## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.18197    0.11530  -1.578
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0  -0.19842    0.12131  -1.636
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.31412    0.11710  -2.683
## TreatParmGA3.750.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.11570    0.11181  -1.035
##
##                                     Pr(>|z|)
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.250.d == 0    0.01301 *
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0    0.16576
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0    0.00189 **
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0   2.33e-05 ***
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0    0.28865
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0    0.57944
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0  0.11451
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0    0.10192
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0  0.00731 **
## TreatParmGA3.750.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0  0.30076
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)
confint(eryngium.ga.pairwise.d, calpha = 1.96)

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -
##       1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
##                                     Estimate lwr      upr
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.250.d == 0   -0.30430 -0.54444 -0.06415
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0   -0.17215 -0.41561  0.07131
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0   -0.37057 -0.60428 -0.13685
## TreatParmGA3.0.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0  -0.48627 -0.71158 -0.26096
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.500.d == 0    0.13214 -0.11195  0.37624
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0  -0.06627 -0.30065  0.16810
## TreatParmGA3.250.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.18197 -0.40797  0.04402
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.750.d == 0  -0.19842 -0.43619  0.03935
## TreatParmGA3.500.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.31412 -0.54363 -0.08461
## TreatParmGA3.750.d - TreatParmGA3.1000.d == 0 -0.11570 -0.33485  0.10345

```

Comparisons for the parameter t50:

```

eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.e <-
  c("TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.250.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e = 0",
    "TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e = 0",

```

```

"TreatParmGA3.750.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e = 0")
eryngium.ga.pairwise.e <- glht(eryngium.ga.meta1,
                              linfct = eryngium.ga.pairWiseComp.e)
summary(eryngium.ga.pairwise.e, test = adjusted("none"))

##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error z value
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.250.e == 0 1.10113 1.27445 0.864
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0 1.15211 1.29657 0.889
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 0.77699 1.24852 0.622
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.86252 1.29118 0.668
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0 0.05098 1.07002 0.048
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 -0.32413 1.01127 -0.321
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 -0.23861 1.06349 -0.224
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 -0.37512 1.03900 -0.361
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 -0.28959 1.08990 -0.266
## TreatParmGA3.750.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.08553 1.03228 0.083
##
## Pr(>|z|)
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.250.e == 0 0.388
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0 0.374
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 0.534
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.504
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0 0.962
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 0.749
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.822
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 0.718
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.790
## TreatParmGA3.750.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 0.934
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)
confint(eryngium.ga.pairwise.e, calpha = 1.96)

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = eryngium.ga.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~TreatParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Rep), struct = "UN", data = eryngium.ga.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr upr
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.250.e == 0 1.10113 -1.39679 3.59904
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0 1.15211 -1.38916 3.69338

```

```
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0    0.77699 -1.67010  3.22409
## TreatParmGA3.0.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0   0.86252 -1.66820  3.39324
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.500.e == 0  0.05098 -2.04626  2.14822
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 -0.32413 -2.30622  1.65795
## TreatParmGA3.250.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 -0.23861 -2.32305  1.84584
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.750.e == 0 -0.37512 -2.41157  1.66133
## TreatParmGA3.500.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0 -0.28959 -2.42580  1.84662
## TreatParmGA3.750.e - TreatParmGA3.1000.e == 0  0.08553 -1.93774  2.10880
```

Comparison to the ordinary two-step approach

We can also fit a linear mixed model just for t50 using the data from Step 1 in the wide format directly:

```
eryngium.ga.wide.data <- eryngium.ga.step1[["wide"]]

eryngium.ga.meta1.t50 <- rma.mv(e.est, e.se,
                               mods = ~ Treat-1,
                               random = ~1|Rep,
                               data = eryngium.ga.wide.data)

summary(eryngium.ga.meta1.t50)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 15; method: REML)
##
##   logLik  Deviance      AIC      BIC      AICc
## -16.9988  33.9975  45.9975  47.8131  73.9975
##
## Variance Components:
##
##           estim  sqrt  nlvls  fixed  factor
## sigma^2    0.8626  0.9287    15    no    Rep
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 10) = 19.2304, p-val = 0.0374
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 1:5):
## QM(df = 5) = 1233.1914, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##           estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb      ci.ub
## TreatGA3.0      12.8932  0.8998  14.3283 <.0001  11.1295  14.6568 ***
## TreatGA3.1000   12.1165  0.7617  15.9072 <.0001  10.6236  13.6094 ***
## TreatGA3.250    11.9306  0.7473  15.9649 <.0001  10.4659  13.3952 ***
## TreatGA3.500    11.8339  0.7690  15.3887 <.0001  10.3267  13.3411 ***
## TreatGA3.750    12.2786  0.7297  16.8275 <.0001  10.8484  13.7087 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

eryngium.ga.t50.pairWiseComp <-
  c("TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.250 = 0",
    "TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.500 = 0",
```

```

"TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.750 = 0",
"TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.1000 = 0",
"TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.500 = 0",
"TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.750 = 0",
"TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.1000 = 0",
"TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.750 = 0",
"TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.1000 = 0",
"TreatGA3.750 - TreatGA3.1000 = 0")

eryngium.ga.t50.pairwise <- glht(eryngium.ga.meta1.t50,
                               linfct = eryngium.ga.t50.pairwiseComp)

summary(eryngium.ga.t50.pairwise, test = adjusted("none"))

```

```

##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = e.est, V = e.se, mods = ~Treat - 1, random = ~1 |
## Rep, data = eryngium.ga.wide.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error z value Pr(>|z|)
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.250 == 0 0.96260 1.16969 0.823 0.411
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.500 == 0 1.05928 1.18367 0.895 0.371
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 0.61458 1.15851 0.530 0.596
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 0.77662 1.17894 0.659 0.510
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.500 == 0 0.09668 1.07230 0.090 0.928
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 -0.34802 1.04445 -0.333 0.739
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 -0.18598 1.06707 -0.174 0.862
## TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 -0.44471 1.06009 -0.419 0.675
## TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 -0.28266 1.08238 -0.261 0.794
## TreatGA3.750 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 0.16205 1.05481 0.154 0.878
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)

```

```

confint(eryngium.ga.t50.pairwise, calpha = 1.96)

```

```

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = e.est, V = e.se, mods = ~Treat - 1, random = ~1 |
## Rep, data = eryngium.ga.wide.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr upr
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.250 == 0 0.96260 -1.32999 3.25519
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.500 == 0 1.05928 -1.26071 3.37927
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 0.61458 -1.65609 2.88525
## TreatGA3.0 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 0.77662 -1.53410 3.08734
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.500 == 0 0.09668 -2.00502 2.19838
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 -0.34802 -2.39515 1.69911

```

```
## TreatGA3.250 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 -0.18598 -2.27744 1.90549
## TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.750 == 0 -0.44471 -2.52248 1.63307
## TreatGA3.500 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 -0.28266 -2.40413 1.83881
## TreatGA3.750 - TreatGA3.1000 == 0 0.16205 -1.90537 2.22947
```

Compared to the joint model the single-parameter model using the original two-step approach resulted in slightly wider 95% confidence intervals.

Extracting the relevant information for plotting accumulated observed data

```
eryngium.ga.rawdata.0 <- makeRawData(subset(eryngium.ga, Treat == "GA3.0"),
                                     "Rep", "Start", "Germinated")
head(eryngium.ga.rawdata.0)
```

```
##   Time Germinated
## 1    0 0.00000000
## 2    2 0.00000000
## 3    4 0.00000000
## 4    7 0.00000000
## 5    9 0.04166667
## 6   11 0.10416667
```

```
eryngium.ga.rawdata.1000 <- makeRawData(subset(eryngium.ga, Treat == "GA3.1000"),
                                         "Rep", "Start", "Germinated")
head(eryngium.ga.rawdata.1000)
```

```
##   Time Germinated
## 1    0 0.00000000
## 2    2 0.00000000
## 3    4 0.00000000
## 4    7 0.00000000
## 5    9 0.10416667
## 6   11 0.27083333
```

Extracting the relevant information for plotting fitted germination curves

```
eryngium.ga.plotdata.0 <- makePlotData(eryngium.ga.meta1, "TreatParmGA3.0", c(1, 35))
head(eryngium.ga.plotdata.0)
```

```
##      Time      Fitted      SE      LCI      UCI
## 1 1.000000 5.361362e-08 2.148720e-07 -3.675277e-07 4.747550e-07
## 2 1.343434 3.251654e-07 1.153576e-06 -1.935803e-06 2.586134e-06
## 3 1.686869 1.305345e-06 4.168951e-06 -6.865648e-06 9.476338e-06
## 4 2.030303 4.046619e-06 1.176125e-05 -1.900500e-05 2.709824e-05
## 5 2.373737 1.050696e-05 2.799937e-05 -4.437078e-05 6.538471e-05
## 6 2.717172 2.397502e-05 5.889703e-05 -9.146104e-05 1.394111e-04
```

```
eryngium.ga.plotdata.1000 <- makePlotData(eryngium.ga.meta1, "TreatParmGA3.1000", c(1, 35))
head(eryngium.ga.plotdata.1000)
```

```
##      Time      Fitted      SE      LCI      UCI
## 1 1.000000 3.983058e-08 1.113281e-07 -1.783685e-07 2.580297e-07
## 2 1.343434 2.928832e-07 7.190105e-07 -1.116351e-06 1.702118e-06
## 3 1.686869 1.364004e-06 2.992004e-06 -4.500216e-06 7.228223e-06
```

```
## 4 2.030303 4.771877e-06 9.455609e-06 -1.376078e-05 2.330453e-05
## 5 2.373737 1.372010e-05 2.474349e-05 -3.477625e-05 6.221646e-05
## 6 2.717172 3.419257e-05 5.642358e-05 -7.639562e-05 1.447808e-04
```

Visualization

Making a plot for treatments 0 and 1000:

```
eryngium.ga.plot1 <- ggplot(eryngium.ga, aes(x = End, y = Germinated)) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 31), ylim = c(0, 1)) +
  xlab("Time (days)") + ylab("Proportion germinated") +
  theme_bw() + ## white background

  # treatment 0
  geom_line(data = eryngium.ga.plotdata.0, aes(x = Time, y = Fitted), # fitted curve
            linetype = "dotted") +
  geom_ribbon(data = eryngium.ga.plotdata.0, # confidence band
             aes(x = Time, y = Fitted, ymin = pmax(0, LCI), ymax = UCI),
             alpha = 0.2) +

  # treatment 1000
  geom_line(data = eryngium.ga.plotdata.1000, aes(x = Time, y = Fitted), # fitted curve
            linetype = "dashed") +
  geom_ribbon(data = eryngium.ga.plotdata.1000, # confidence band
             aes(x = Time, y = Fitted, ymin = pmax(0, LCI), ymax = UCI),
             alpha = 0.2) +

  # adding accumulated observed data
  geom_point(data = eryngium.ga.rawdata.0,
             aes(x = Time, y = Germinated)) +
  geom_point(data = eryngium.ga.rawdata.1000,
             aes(x = Time, y = Germinated))

eryngium.ga.plot1
```


Adding text to the plot:

```

eryngium.ga.plot2 <- eryngium.ga.plot1 +
  annotate("text", x = 20, y = 0.85, label = "1000 ppm GA3") +
  annotate("text", x = 22, y = 0.42, label = "0 ppm GA3")

```

```
eryngium.ga.plot2
```


Saving the plot:

```
jpeg("/home/christian/stat/manuscripts/2020/Two-step2/ex1-v3.jpg")
eryngium.ga.plot2
dev.off()
```

```
## pdf
## 2
```

Example 2

Step 1

Fitting event-time models in a loop:

```
blackgrass.step1 <- makeStep1Data("Ger", "Start.Day", "End.Day",
                                  LL.3(), blackgrass,
                                  c("Exp", "Bio", "Depth", "Temp", "Pot"))
```

```
## Error in optim(startVec, opfct, hessian = TRUE, method = optMethod, control = list(maxit = maxIt, :
## oprindeligt værdi i 'vmin' er ikke finitte
```

You can ignore the error message. It means that no fit was achieved in a few cases (explored in detail below).

Looking at the output: The parameter estimates for the top 6 rows:

```
dim(blackgrass.step1[["wide"]])
```

```
## [1] 128 12
```

```
head(blackgrass.step1[["wide"]])
```

```
##   Exp Bio Depth Temp Pot      b.est      b.se      d.est      d.se      e.est
## 1  1  R    0   10  1  -7.454884 1.544786 0.6983622 0.08645511 686.5420
## 2  1  R    0   10 33  -9.852617 1.818852 0.8253547 0.06951696 708.4872
## 3  1  R    0   10 65  -8.603972 1.629193 0.8370523 0.07288557 708.1560
## 4  1  R    0   10 97 -15.879871 2.427124 0.9176293 0.04612097 670.1672
## 5  1  R    0   17 17  -5.979492 1.150864 0.8557436 0.07926434 331.9176
## 6  1  R    0   17 49  -9.379640 2.035842 0.7047473 0.08888001 389.0945
##           e.se npar
## 1 36.02073    3
## 2 24.27229    3
## 3 28.93710    3
## 4 12.96091    3
## 5 20.41103    3
## 6 16.38329    3
```

Finding the treatment combinations not resulting in a model fit:

```
blackgrass.step1[["wide"]][is.na(blackgrass.step1[["wide"]][, "b.est"]), ]
```

```
##   Exp Bio Depth Temp Pot b.est b.se d.est d.se e.est e.se npar
## 25  1  R    6   10 13    NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
## 26  1  R    6   10 45    NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
## 94  2  R    6   17 62    NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
## 96  2  R    6   17 126   NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
## 99  2  S    0   10 68    NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
## 126 2  S    6   17 64    NA  NA   NA  NA   NA  NA    0
```

Looking at the data for the the combinations where no fits were obtained:

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 1 & Bio == "R" & Depth == 6 & Temp == 10 & Pot == 13)
```

```
##   Exp Temp Popu Bio Depth Rep Start.Day End.Day Ger Accum.Ger TotalSeed Pot
## 617  1  10  914  R    6  1           0    360  0           0      36 13
## 618  1  10  914  R    6  1          360    376  0           0      36 13
## 619  1  10  914  R    6  1          376    384  0           0      36 13
## 620  1  10  914  R    6  1          384    400  0           0      36 13
## 621  1  10  914  R    6  1          400    408  0           0      36 13
## 622  1  10  914  R    6  1          408    424  0           0      36 13
## 623  1  10  914  R    6  1          424    432  0           0      36 13
## 624  1  10  914  R    6  1          432    480  0           0      36 13
## 625  1  10  914  R    6  1          480    504  0           0      36 13
## 626  1  10  914  R    6  1          504    528  0           0      36 13
## 627  1  10  914  R    6  1          528    552  0           0      36 13
## 628  1  10  914  R    6  1          552    576  0           0      36 13
## 629  1  10  914  R    6  1          576    600  0           0      36 13
## 630  1  10  914  R    6  1          600    624  0           0      36 13
## 631  1  10  914  R    6  1          624    672  0           0      36 13
## 632  1  10  914  R    6  1          672    696  0           0      36 13
## 633  1  10  914  R    6  1          696    720  0           0      36 13
## 634  1  10  914  R    6  1          720    792  0           0      36 13
## 635  1  10  914  R    6  1          792    864  0           0      36 13
## 636  1  10  914  R    6  1          864    936  0           0      36 13
## 637  1  10  914  R    6  1          936   1032  0           0      36 13
## 638  1  10  914  R    6  1         1032    Inf  36           NA      36 13
```

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 1 & Bio == "R" & Depth == 6 & Temp == 10 & Pot == 45)
```

##	Exp	Temp	Popu	Bio	Depth	Rep	Start.Day	End.Day	Ger	Accum.Ger	TotalSeed	Pot
## 639	1	10	914	R	6	2	0	360	0	0	36	45
## 640	1	10	914	R	6	2	360	376	0	0	36	45
## 641	1	10	914	R	6	2	376	384	0	0	36	45
## 642	1	10	914	R	6	2	384	400	0	0	36	45
## 643	1	10	914	R	6	2	400	408	0	0	36	45
## 644	1	10	914	R	6	2	408	424	0	0	36	45
## 645	1	10	914	R	6	2	424	432	0	0	36	45
## 646	1	10	914	R	6	2	432	480	0	0	36	45
## 647	1	10	914	R	6	2	480	504	0	0	36	45
## 648	1	10	914	R	6	2	504	528	0	0	36	45
## 649	1	10	914	R	6	2	528	552	0	0	36	45
## 650	1	10	914	R	6	2	552	576	0	0	36	45
## 651	1	10	914	R	6	2	576	600	0	0	36	45
## 652	1	10	914	R	6	2	600	624	0	0	36	45
## 653	1	10	914	R	6	2	624	672	0	0	36	45
## 654	1	10	914	R	6	2	672	696	0	0	36	45
## 655	1	10	914	R	6	2	696	720	0	0	36	45
## 656	1	10	914	R	6	2	720	792	0	0	36	45
## 657	1	10	914	R	6	2	792	864	0	0	36	45
## 658	1	10	914	R	6	2	864	936	0	0	36	45
## 659	1	10	914	R	6	2	936	1032	0	0	36	45
## 660	1	10	914	R	6	2	1032	Inf	36	NA	36	45

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 2 & Bio == "R" & Depth == 6 & Temp == 17 & Pot == 62)
```

##	Exp	Temp	Popu	Bio	Depth	Rep	Start.Day	End.Day	Ger	Accum.Ger	TotalSeed	Pot
## 2690	2	17	914	R	6	2	0	168	0	0	36	62
## 2691	2	17	914	R	6	2	168	184	0	0	36	62
## 2692	2	17	914	R	6	2	184	192	0	0	36	62
## 2693	2	17	914	R	6	2	192	208	0	0	36	62
## 2694	2	17	914	R	6	2	208	216	0	0	36	62
## 2695	2	17	914	R	6	2	216	232	0	0	36	62
## 2696	2	17	914	R	6	2	232	240	0	0	36	62
## 2697	2	17	914	R	6	2	240	256	0	0	36	62
## 2698	2	17	914	R	6	2	256	264	0	0	36	62
## 2699	2	17	914	R	6	2	264	288	0	0	36	62
## 2700	2	17	914	R	6	2	288	312	0	0	36	62
## 2701	2	17	914	R	6	2	312	336	0	0	36	62
## 2702	2	17	914	R	6	2	336	360	0	0	36	62
## 2703	2	17	914	R	6	2	360	384	0	0	36	62
## 2704	2	17	914	R	6	2	384	408	0	0	36	62
## 2705	2	17	914	R	6	2	408	432	0	0	36	62
## 2706	2	17	914	R	6	2	432	456	0	0	36	62
## 2707	2	17	914	R	6	2	456	480	0	0	36	62
## 2708	2	17	914	R	6	2	480	504	0	0	36	62
## 2709	2	17	914	R	6	2	504	528	0	0	36	62
## 2710	2	17	914	R	6	2	528	Inf	36	NA	36	62

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 2 & Bio == "R" & Depth == 6 & Temp == 17 & Pot == 126)
```

##	Exp	Temp	Popu	Bio	Depth	Rep	Start.Day	End.Day	Ger	Accum.Ger	TotalSeed	Pot
## 2732	2	17	914	R	6	4	0	168	0	0	36	126

```

## 2733  2  17  914  R    6  4    168   184  0    0    36 126
## 2734  2  17  914  R    6  4    184   192  0    0    36 126
## 2735  2  17  914  R    6  4    192   208  0    0    36 126
## 2736  2  17  914  R    6  4    208   216  0    0    36 126
## 2737  2  17  914  R    6  4    216   232  0    0    36 126
## 2738  2  17  914  R    6  4    232   240  0    0    36 126
## 2739  2  17  914  R    6  4    240   256  0    0    36 126
## 2740  2  17  914  R    6  4    256   264  0    0    36 126
## 2741  2  17  914  R    6  4    264   288  0    0    36 126
## 2742  2  17  914  R    6  4    288   312  0    0    36 126
## 2743  2  17  914  R    6  4    312   336  0    0    36 126
## 2744  2  17  914  R    6  4    336   360  0    0    36 126
## 2745  2  17  914  R    6  4    360   384  0    0    36 126
## 2746  2  17  914  R    6  4    384   408  0    0    36 126
## 2747  2  17  914  R    6  4    408   432  0    0    36 126
## 2748  2  17  914  R    6  4    432   456  0    0    36 126
## 2749  2  17  914  R    6  4    456   480  0    0    36 126
## 2750  2  17  914  R    6  4    480   504  0    0    36 126
## 2751  2  17  914  R    6  4    504   528  0    0    36 126
## 2752  2  17  914  R    6  4    528   Inf  36    NA    36 126

```

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 2 & Bio == "S" & Depth == 0 & Temp == 10 & Pot == 68)
```

```

##      Exp Temp Popu Bio Depth Rep Start.Day End.Day Ger Accum.Ger TotalSeed Pot
## 749   2   10  914  S    0  3      0    360  0      0      36  68
## 750   2   10  914  S    0  3    360    376  0      0      36  68
## 751   2   10  914  S    0  3    376    384  3      3      36  68
## 752   2   10  914  S    0  3    384    400  4      7      36  68
## 753   2   10  914  S    0  3    400    408  1      8      36  68
## 754   2   10  914  S    0  3    408    424  2     10      36  68
## 755   2   10  914  S    0  3    424    432  0     10      36  68
## 756   2   10  914  S    0  3    432    480 11     21      36  68
## 757   2   10  914  S    0  3    480    504  2     23      36  68
## 758   2   10  914  S    0  3    504    528  6     29      36  68
## 759   2   10  914  S    0  3    528    552  5     34      36  68
## 760   2   10  914  S    0  3    552    576  0     34      36  68
## 761   2   10  914  S    0  3    576    600  0     34      36  68
## 762   2   10  914  S    0  3    600    624  0     34      36  68
## 763   2   10  914  S    0  3    624    672  0     34      36  68
## 764   2   10  914  S    0  3    672    696  1     35      36  68
## 765   2   10  914  S    0  3    696    720  0     35      36  68
## 766   2   10  914  S    0  3    720    792  1     36      36  68
## 767   2   10  914  S    0  3    792    864  0     36      36  68
## 768   2   10  914  S    0  3    864    936  0     36      36  68
## 769   2   10  914  S    0  3    936   1032  0     36      36  68
## 770   2   10  914  S    0  3   1032   Inf  0     NA      36  68

```

```
subset(blackgrass, Exp == 2 & Bio == "S" & Depth == 6 & Temp == 17 & Pot == 64)
```

```

##      Exp Temp Popu Bio Depth Rep Start.Day End.Day Ger Accum.Ger TotalSeed Pot
## 2354  2   17  914  S    6  2      0    168  0      0      36  64
## 2355  2   17  914  S    6  2    168    184  0      0      36  64
## 2356  2   17  914  S    6  2    184    192  0      0      36  64
## 2357  2   17  914  S    6  2    192    208  0      0      36  64
## 2358  2   17  914  S    6  2    208    216  0      0      36  64

```

```
## 2359 2 17 914 S 6 2 216 232 0 0 36 64
## 2360 2 17 914 S 6 2 232 240 0 0 36 64
## 2361 2 17 914 S 6 2 240 256 0 0 36 64
## 2362 2 17 914 S 6 2 256 264 0 0 36 64
## 2363 2 17 914 S 6 2 264 288 0 0 36 64
## 2364 2 17 914 S 6 2 288 312 0 0 36 64
## 2365 2 17 914 S 6 2 312 336 0 0 36 64
## 2366 2 17 914 S 6 2 336 360 0 0 36 64
## 2367 2 17 914 S 6 2 360 384 0 0 36 64
## 2368 2 17 914 S 6 2 384 408 0 0 36 64
## 2369 2 17 914 S 6 2 408 432 0 0 36 64
## 2370 2 17 914 S 6 2 432 456 0 0 36 64
## 2371 2 17 914 S 6 2 456 480 0 0 36 64
## 2372 2 17 914 S 6 2 480 504 0 0 36 64
## 2373 2 17 914 S 6 2 504 528 0 0 36 64
## 2374 2 17 914 S 6 2 528 Inf 36 NA 36 64
```

For the 5 pots at depth 6 no germination was observed and therefore no germination curve can be fitted. They remain missing values in Step 2. However, for the pot at depth 0 it should be possible to fit a germination: as all seeds germinated in that pot the model function need to be changed from LL.3() to LL.2() (the upper limit is set to 1, it need not be estimated).

Manual fitting of the single missing combination where there is information available using a two-parameter log-logistic model:

```
blackgrass.step1.2.S.0.10.68 <-
  drm(Ger ~ Start.Day + End.Day,
      data = subset(blackgrass, Exp == 2 & Bio == "S" & Depth == 0 & Temp == 10 & Pot == 68),
      fct = LL.2(),
      type = "event")
plot(blackgrass.step1.2.S.0.10.68)
```



```
summary(blackgrass.step1.2.S.0.10.68)
```

```
##
## Model fitted: Log-logistic (ED50 as parameter) with lower limit at 0 and upper limit at 1 (2 parms)
##
## Parameter estimates:
##
##           Estimate Std. Error t-value  p-value
## b:(Intercept) -11.7657      1.6337 -7.2017 5.949e-13 ***
## e:(Intercept)  467.5751     11.7207 39.8931 < 2.2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

Adding the model fit from the manual fitting to the list of model fits from the automated run:

```
blackgrass.step1[["fits"]][["2.S.0.10.68"]] <- blackgrass.step1.2.S.0.10.68
blackgrass.step2 <- updateStep1Data(blackgrass.step1[["fits"]],
                                   c("Exp", "Bio", "Depth", "Temp", "Pot"))
```

Extracting data for Step 2

The element named “long” contains the data in the long format and a large (block-diagonal) variance-covariance matrix that carries information about the correlations between parameter estimates:

```
blackgrass.long <- blackgrass.step2[["long"]]
names(blackgrass.long)
```

```
## [1] "data"      "vcovMat"
```

Showing the top lines of the data in the long format:

```
blackgrass.long.data <- blackgrass.long[["data"]]
dim(blackgrass.long.data)
```

```
## [1] 368  14
```

```
head(blackgrass.long.data, 20)
```

```
##      Exp Bio Depth Temp Pot      b.est      b.se      d.est      d.se      e.est
## 1      1  R      0  10   1  -7.454884  1.544786  0.6983622  0.08645511  686.5420
## 1.1    1  R      0  10   1  -7.454884  1.544786  0.6983622  0.08645511  686.5420
## 1.2    1  R      0  10   1  -7.454884  1.544786  0.6983622  0.08645511  686.5420
## 2      1  R      0  10  33  -9.852617  1.818852  0.8253547  0.06951696  708.4872
## 2.1    1  R      0  10  33  -9.852617  1.818852  0.8253547  0.06951696  708.4872
## 2.2    1  R      0  10  33  -9.852617  1.818852  0.8253547  0.06951696  708.4872
## 3      1  R      0  10  65  -8.603972  1.629193  0.8370523  0.07288557  708.1560
## 3.1    1  R      0  10  65  -8.603972  1.629193  0.8370523  0.07288557  708.1560
## 3.2    1  R      0  10  65  -8.603972  1.629193  0.8370523  0.07288557  708.1560
## 4      1  R      0  10  97 -15.879871  2.427124  0.9176293  0.04612097  670.1672
## 4.1    1  R      0  10  97 -15.879871  2.427124  0.9176293  0.04612097  670.1672
## 4.2    1  R      0  10  97 -15.879871  2.427124  0.9176293  0.04612097  670.1672
## 5      1  R      0  17  17  -5.979492  1.150864  0.8557436  0.07926434  331.9176
## 5.1    1  R      0  17  17  -5.979492  1.150864  0.8557436  0.07926434  331.9176
## 5.2    1  R      0  17  17  -5.979492  1.150864  0.8557436  0.07926434  331.9176
## 6      1  R      0  17  49  -9.379640  2.035842  0.7047473  0.08888001  389.0945
```

```
## 6.1 1 R 0 17 49 -9.379640 2.035842 0.7047473 0.08888001 389.0945
## 6.2 1 R 0 17 49 -9.379640 2.035842 0.7047473 0.08888001 389.0945
## 7 1 R 0 17 81 -5.166254 1.118968 0.9325931 0.12207966 369.2870
## 7.1 1 R 0 17 81 -5.166254 1.118968 0.9325931 0.12207966 369.2870
## e.se npar Parm Resp
## 1 36.02073 3 b -7.4548835
## 1.1 36.02073 3 d 0.6983622
## 1.2 36.02073 3 e 686.5419940
## 2 24.27229 3 b -9.8526168
## 2.1 24.27229 3 d 0.8253547
## 2.2 24.27229 3 e 708.4871631
## 3 28.93710 3 b -8.6039722
## 3.1 28.93710 3 d 0.8370523
## 3.2 28.93710 3 e 708.1560182
## 4 12.96091 3 b -15.8798706
## 4.1 12.96091 3 d 0.9176293
## 4.2 12.96091 3 e 670.1671990
## 5 20.41103 3 b -5.9794923
## 5.1 20.41103 3 d 0.8557436
## 5.2 20.41103 3 e 331.9175968
## 6 16.38329 3 b -9.3796401
## 6.1 16.38329 3 d 0.7047473
## 6.2 16.38329 3 e 389.0944967
## 7 32.47330 3 b -5.1662541
## 7.1 32.47330 3 d 0.9325931
```

Step 2

Defining an explicit four-way interaction term:

```
blackgrass.long.data[["BioDepthTempParm"]] <-
  with(blackgrass.long.data, interaction(Bio, Depth, Temp, Parm))
```

Fitting the meta analysis model (Note: the response variable is always called "Resp"):

```
blackgrass.meta1 <- rma.mv(Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]],
  mods = ~ BioDepthTempParm-1,
  random = list(~Parm|Exp, ~ Parm|Pot),
  data = blackgrass.long.data,
  struct = "UN") # the simpler "DIAG" gives almost the same result
```

```
## Warning in rma.mv(Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods =
## ~BioDepthTempParm - : Ratio of largest to smallest sampling variance extremely
## large. May not be able to obtain stable results.
```

```
summary(blackgrass.meta1)
```

```
##
## Multivariate Meta-Analysis Model (k = 368; method: REML)
##
## logLik Deviance AIC BIC AICc
## -728.7298 1457.4596 1577.4596 1803.5588 1605.7221
##
## Variance Components:
##
```

```

## outer factor: Exp (nlvls = 2)
## inner factor: Parm (nlvls = 3)
##
##          estim      sqrt  k.lvl  fixed  level
## tau^2.1    0.7765  0.8812   123    no    b
## tau^2.2    0.0009  0.0295   122    no    d
## tau^2.3   74.0773  8.6068   123    no    e
##
##      rho.b  rho.d  rho.e    b  d  e
## b         1  1.0000  1.0000   - no no
## d  1.0000         1  1.0000    2  - no
## e  1.0000  1.0000         1    2  2  -
##
## outer factor: Pot (nlvls = 123)
## inner factor: Parm (nlvls = 3)
##
##          estim      sqrt  k.lvl  fixed  level
## gamma^2.1  0.5392  0.7343   123    no    b
## gamma^2.2  0.0050  0.0705   122    no    d
## gamma^2.3 789.9778 28.1065   123    no    e
##
##      phi.b  phi.d  phi.e    b  d  e
## b         1 -0.7589  0.6717   - no no
## d -0.7589         1 -0.2278   122  - no
## e  0.6717 -0.2278         1   123 122  -
##
## Test for Residual Heterogeneity:
## QE(df = 320) = 879.4453, p-val < .0001
##
## Test of Moderators (coefficients 1:48):
## QM(df = 48) = 30139.9856, p-val < .0001
##
## Model Results:
##
##          estimate      se      zval      pval      ci.lb
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b -9.9737  0.9447 -10.5578 <.0001 -11.8252
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b -10.0260  0.8770 -11.4318 <.0001 -11.7450
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b -7.9951  0.9093 -8.7929 <.0001 -9.7773
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b -8.3164  0.8280 -10.0435 <.0001 -9.9393
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b -9.9740  0.9939 -10.0352 <.0001 -11.9220
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b -9.1003  0.8754 -10.3954 <.0001 -10.8160
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b -7.0561  1.5252 -4.6264 <.0001 -10.0455
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b -10.6280  1.1241 -9.4546 <.0001 -12.8312
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b -6.7739  0.8521 -7.9501 <.0001 -8.4439
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b -6.0393  0.7882 -7.6618 <.0001 -7.5841
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b -11.2651  1.0422 -10.8088 <.0001 -13.3078
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b -12.6821  1.0485 -12.0957 <.0001 -14.7371
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b -14.5689  1.2021 -12.1199 <.0001 -16.9249
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b -14.0036  1.1039 -12.6860 <.0001 -16.1671
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b -9.7606  1.9210 -5.0809 <.0001 -13.5258
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b -9.5490  1.5876 -6.0148 <.0001 -12.6606
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d  0.7510  0.0420  17.8959 <.0001  0.6687
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d  0.8962  0.0397  22.5949 <.0001  0.8184
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d  0.4745  0.0432  10.9890 <.0001  0.3899

```

## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d	0.7749	0.0408	18.9913	<.0001	0.6950
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d	0.4990	0.0435	11.4829	<.0001	0.4139
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d	0.7207	0.0417	17.2766	<.0001	0.6389
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d	0.1138	0.0419	2.7172	0.0066	0.0317
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d	0.3777	0.0428	8.8232	<.0001	0.2938
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d	0.7011	0.0479	14.6503	<.0001	0.6073
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d	0.8468	0.0463	18.2706	<.0001	0.7560
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d	0.5790	0.0432	13.4007	<.0001	0.4943
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d	0.6918	0.0421	16.4448	<.0001	0.6094
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d	0.5739	0.0436	13.1751	<.0001	0.4885
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d	0.6963	0.0421	16.5462	<.0001	0.6138
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d	0.0893	0.0403	2.2145	0.0268	0.0103
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d	0.1352	0.0396	3.4133	0.0006	0.0576
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e	695.9239	14.9201	46.6434	<.0001	666.6810
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e	627.9829	13.8496	45.3431	<.0001	600.8383
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e	507.8220	15.0523	33.7371	<.0001	478.3200
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e	479.4921	13.4946	35.5322	<.0001	453.0432
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e	524.7479	14.1213	37.1601	<.0001	497.0707
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e	463.8542	13.1971	35.1481	<.0001	437.9883
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e	612.6748	26.3749	23.2294	<.0001	560.9809
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e	587.2229	14.9650	39.2399	<.0001	557.8922
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e	370.6081	14.2027	26.0942	<.0001	342.7713
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e	381.5337	13.8648	27.5181	<.0001	354.3591
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e	226.0802	11.9639	18.8968	<.0001	202.6313
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e	213.0892	11.8294	18.0135	<.0001	189.9040
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e	227.8506	11.8569	19.2168	<.0001	204.6116
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e	211.6203	11.7912	17.9473	<.0001	188.5099
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e	303.0455	16.3473	18.5379	<.0001	271.0053
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e	265.0241	13.7562	19.2657	<.0001	238.0623
##	ci.ub				
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b	-8.1221	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b	-8.3071	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b	-6.2130	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b	-6.6935	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b	-8.0260	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b	-7.3845	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b	-4.0668	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b	-8.4248	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b	-5.1039	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b	-4.4944	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b	-9.2224	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b	-10.6271	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b	-12.2129	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b	-11.8400	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b	-5.9954	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b	-6.4373	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d	0.8332	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d	0.9739	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d	0.5591	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d	0.8549	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d	0.5842	***			
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d	0.8024	***			
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d	0.1959	**			
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d	0.4616	***			

```

## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d    0.7949 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d    0.9377 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d    0.6637 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d    0.7743 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d    0.6593 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d    0.7788 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d    0.1683  *
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d    0.2129 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e   725.1668 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e   655.1276 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e   537.3240 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e   505.9410 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e   552.4250 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e   489.7201 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e   664.3687 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e   616.5537 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e   398.4449 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e   408.7083 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e   249.5290 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e   236.2745 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e   251.0897 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e   234.7306 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e   335.0856 ***
## BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e   291.9858 ***
##
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

```

The warning message can be ignored as there is no problem with the estimates being on different scales.

A slightly simpler model assumes uncorrelated parameter estimates (not run here):

```

blackgrass.meta1x <- rma.mv(Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]],
                           mods = ~ BioDepthTempParm-1,
                           random = list(~Parm|Exp, ~ Parm|Pot),
                           data = blackgrass.long.data,
                           struct = "DIAG")

summary(blackgrass.meta1x)

```

Another slightly simpler model ignoring the block structure would be (also not run here):

```

blackgrass.meta1y <- rma.mv(Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]],
                           mods = ~ BioDepthTempParm-1,
                           random = ~ Parm|Pot,
                           data = blackgrass.long.data, struct = "UN")

summary(blackgrass.meta1y)

```

These 2 alternatives result in very similar results.

Graphical model checking

```

plot(fitted(blackgrass.meta1), residuals(blackgrass.meta1, type = "rstandard")) # residual plot

```



```
qqnorm(residuals(blackgrass.meta1, type = "rstandard")) # QQ plot
```

Normal Q-Q Plot

Variation at different levels (estimated SD's)

```
sqrt(summary(blackgrass.meta1)[["sigma2"]]) # between blocks

## [1] 0

sqrt(summary(blackgrass.meta1)[["tau2"]]) # between pots within each model parameter

## [1] 0.88116410 0.02949208 8.60681985
```

Comparison of treatment combinations

Comparisons for the parameter b:

```
targetedPairWiseComp.b <-
  c("BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b = 0")

blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.b <- glht(blackgrass.meta1,
                                       linfct = targetedPairWiseComp.b)

summary(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.b, test = adjusted("none"))

##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b == 0 0.05237 0.94062
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b == 0 0.32127 0.85809
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b == 0 -0.87375 0.98865
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b == 0 3.57184 1.67795
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b == 0 -0.73467 0.75278
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b == 0 1.41699 1.18718
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b == 0 -0.56531 1.37266
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b == 0 -0.21163 2.32593
##
## z value Pr(>|z|)
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b == 0 0.056 0.9556
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b == 0 0.374 0.7081
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b == 0 -0.884 0.3768
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b == 0 2.129 0.0333 *
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b == 0 -0.976 0.3291
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b == 0 1.194 0.2326
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b == 0 -0.412 0.6805
```

```

## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b == 0 -0.091 0.9275
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)
confint(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.b, calpha = 1.96)

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b == 0 0.05237 -1.79124
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b == 0 0.32127 -1.36058
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b == 0 -0.87375 -2.81150
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b == 0 3.57184 0.28305
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b == 0 -0.73467 -2.21012
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b == 0 1.41699 -0.90989
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b == 0 -0.56531 -3.25573
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b == 0 -0.21163 -4.77044
## upr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.b == 0 1.89598
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.b == 0 2.00313
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.b == 0 1.06400
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.b == 0 6.86063
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.b == 0 0.74079
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.b == 0 3.74386
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.b == 0 2.12511
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.b - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.b == 0 4.34719

Comparisons for the parameter d:
targetedPairWiseComp.d <-
  c("BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d = 0")

blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.d <- glht(blackgrass.meta1,
  linfct = targetedPairWiseComp.d)

summary(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.d, test = adjusted("none"))

##

```

```

## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d == 0 -0.14520 0.04962
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d == 0 -0.30045 0.05157
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d == 0 -0.22164 0.05252
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d == 0 -0.26389 0.05212
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d == 0 -0.14574 0.05973
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d == 0 -0.11286 0.05260
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d == 0 -0.12243 0.05290
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d == 0 -0.04596 0.04823
##
## z value Pr(>|z|)
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d == 0 -2.926 0.00343 **
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d == 0 -5.826 5.68e-09 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d == 0 -4.220 2.45e-05 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d == 0 -5.063 4.13e-07 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d == 0 -2.440 0.01469 *
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d == 0 -2.146 0.03190 *
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d == 0 -2.314 0.02065 *
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d == 0 -0.953 0.34059
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)

```

```
confint(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.d, calpha = 1.96)
```

```

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d == 0 -0.145199 -0.242454
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d == 0 -0.300453 -0.401533
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d == 0 -0.221640 -0.324589
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d == 0 -0.263894 -0.366057
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d == 0 -0.145741 -0.262816
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d == 0 -0.112860 -0.215956
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d == 0 -0.122433 -0.226120
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d == 0 -0.045960 -0.140484
##
## upr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.d == 0 -0.047944
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.d == 0 -0.199373

```

```
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.d == 0 -0.118691
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.d == 0 -0.161730
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.d == 0 -0.028666
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.d == 0 -0.009765
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.d == 0 -0.018745
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.d - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.d == 0 0.048564
```

Comparisons for the parameter t50:

```
targetedPairWiseComp.e1 <-
  c("BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e = 0",
    "BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e = 0")

blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e1 <- glht(blackgrass.meta1,
                                       linfct = targetedPairWiseComp.e1)

summary(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e1, test = adjusted("none"))
```

```
##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate Std. Error
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e == 0 67.94 18.45
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e == 0 28.33 18.29
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e == 0 60.89 17.31
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e == 0 25.45 29.05
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e == 0 -10.93 17.88
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e == 0 12.99 14.46
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e == 0 16.23 14.34
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e == 0 38.02 19.56
## z value Pr(>|z|)
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e == 0 3.683 0.000231 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e == 0 1.549 0.121435
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e == 0 3.519 0.000434 ***
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e == 0 0.876 0.381031
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e == 0 -0.611 0.541269
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e == 0 0.899 0.368856
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e == 0 1.132 0.257598
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e == 0 1.944 0.051932 .
## ---
## Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## (Adjusted p values reported -- none method)
```

```

confint(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e1, calpha = 1.96)

##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## Estimate lwr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e == 0 67.9410 31.7806
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e == 0 28.3300 -7.5220
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e == 0 60.8937 26.9733
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e == 0 25.4519 -31.4953
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e == 0 -10.9256 -45.9796
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e == 0 12.9909 -15.3440
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e == 0 16.2304 -11.8695
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e == 0 38.0214 -0.3188
##
## upr
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e == 0 104.1014
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e == 0 64.1820
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.10.e == 0 94.8141
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.10.e == 0 82.3991
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.17.e == 0 24.1283
## BioDepthTempParmR.1.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.1.17.e == 0 41.3259
## BioDepthTempParmR.3.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.3.17.e == 0 44.3303
## BioDepthTempParmR.6.17.e - BioDepthTempParmS.6.17.e == 0 76.3616

targetedPairWiseComp.e2 <-
  c("BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e -
    BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e -- BioDepthTempParmS.1.10.e = 0")

blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e2 <- glht(blackgrass.meta1,
  linfct = targetedPairWiseComp.e2)

summary(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e2)

##
## Simultaneous Tests for General Linear Hypotheses
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.

```

```
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
## (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)
```

```
confint(blackgrass.targeted.pairwise.e2)
```

```
##
## Simultaneous Confidence Intervals
##
## Fit: rma.mv(yi = Resp, V = blackgrass.long[["vcovMat"]], mods = ~BioDepthTempParm -
## 1, random = list(~Parm | Exp, ~Parm | Pot), struct = "UN",
## data = blackgrass.long.data)
##
## Quantile = 1.96
## 95% family-wise confidence level
##
## Linear Hypotheses:
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
##
## BioDepthTempParmR.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmS.0.10.e - BioDepthTempParmR.1.10.e - -BioDepthTempParmS.
```

Note that the last of the above comparisons was a difference of a difference, which corresponds to investigating one aspect of the interaction between biotype and depth.

Extracting the relevant information for plotting accumulated observed data

```
blackgrass.rawdata.R.3.10 <-
  makeRawData(subset(blackgrass, Bio == "R" & Depth == 3 & Temp == 10),
              "Pot", "Start.Day", "Ger")
head(blackgrass.rawdata.R.3.10)
```

```
## Time Germinated
## 1 0 0.000000000
## 2 360 0.000000000
## 3 376 0.000000000
## 4 384 0.000000000
## 5 400 0.003472222
## 6 408 0.013888889
```

```
blackgrass.rawdata.S.3.10 <-
  makeRawData(subset(blackgrass, Bio == "S" & Depth == 3 & Temp == 10),
              "Pot", "Start.Day", "Ger")
head(blackgrass.rawdata.S.3.10)
```

```
## Time Germinated
## 1 0 0.000000000
## 2 360 0.000000000
## 3 376 0.000000000
## 4 384 0.03819444
```

```
## 5 400 0.11458333
## 6 408 0.16319444
```

Extracting the relevant information for plotting (as an example for 2 groups)

```
blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10 <- makePlotData(blackgrass.metal, "R.3.10", c(1, 1400))
head(blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10)
```

```
##      Time      Fitted      SE      LCI      UCI
## 1  1.00000 3.709432e-28 2.273917e-27 -4.085852e-27 4.827739e-27
## 2 15.13131 2.174754e-16 7.468159e-16 -1.246257e-15 1.681208e-15
## 3 29.26263 1.564346e-13 4.349993e-13 -6.961483e-13 1.009017e-12
## 4 43.39394 7.962392e-12 1.903807e-11 -2.935154e-11 4.527633e-11
## 5 57.52525 1.324818e-10 2.798811e-10 -4.160750e-10 6.810387e-10
## 6 71.65657 1.184818e-09 2.246456e-09 -3.218154e-09 5.587790e-09
```

```
blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10 <- makePlotData(blackgrass.metal, "S.3.10", c(1, 1400))
head(blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10)
```

```
##      Time      Fitted      SE      LCI      UCI
## 1  1.00000 3.917088e-25 2.059389e-24 -3.644620e-24 4.428038e-24
## 2 15.13131 2.138705e-14 6.166358e-14 -9.947135e-14 1.422454e-13
## 3 29.26263 8.645696e-12 1.995507e-11 -3.046552e-11 4.775691e-11
## 4 43.39394 3.118879e-10 6.129041e-10 -8.893820e-10 1.513158e-09
## 5 57.52525 4.056382e-09 6.977998e-09 -9.620243e-09 1.773301e-08
## 6 71.65657 2.994199e-08 4.580688e-08 -5.983783e-08 1.197218e-07
```

Visualization

The traditional plotting system may be used for a simple plot:

```
plot(0, xlim = c(0, 1100), ylim = c(0, 1), cex = 0, xlab = "Time (hours)",
     ylab = "Proportion germinated", las = 1)

with(blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10, lines(Time, Fitted, type = "l", ylim = c(0, 1)))
with(blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10, lines(Time, LCI, lty = 2))
with(blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10, lines(Time, UCI, lty = 2))

with(blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10, lines(Time, Fitted, type = "l", ylim = c(0, 1),
                                       col = "gray"))
with(blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10, lines(Time, LCI, lty = 2))
with(blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10, lines(Time, UCI, lty = 2))
```


Rendering the plot with fitted curves and confidence bands using "ggplot2":

```
blackgrass.plot1 <- ggplot(blackgrass, aes(x = End.Day, y = Ger)) +
  coord_cartesian(xlim = c(0, 1100), ylim = c(0, 1)) +
  xlab("Time (hours)") + ylab("Proportion germinated") +
  theme_bw() + ## white background

# group R.3.10
geom_line(data = blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10, aes(x = Time, y = Fitted), # fitted curve
  linetype = "dotted") +
geom_ribbon(data = blackgrass.plotdata.R.3.10, # confidence band
  aes(x = Time, y = Fitted, ymin = LCI, ymax = UCI),
  alpha = 0.2) +

# group S.3.10
geom_line(data = blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10, aes(x = Time, y = Fitted), # fitted curve
  linetype = "dashed") +
geom_ribbon(data = blackgrass.plotdata.S.3.10, # confidence band
  aes(x = Time, y = Fitted, ymin = LCI, ymax = UCI),
  alpha = 0.2)

blackgrass.plot1
```


Adding the cumulated observed data:

```
blackgrass.plot2 <- blackgrass.plot1 +  
  
  geom_point(data = blackgrass.rawdata.R.3.10,  
            aes(x = Time, y = Germinated)) +  
  geom_point(data = blackgrass.rawdata.S.3.10,  
            aes(x = Time, y = Germinated))  
  
blackgrass.plot2
```


Adding text to the plot using the plotmath functionality in **R**:

```
blackgrass.plot3 <- blackgrass.plot2 +
  annotate("text", x = 900, y = 0.37, label = "Resistant biotype:") +
  annotate("text", x = 1000, y = 0.34,
    label = "paste(\"Depth 3 cm, Temperature \", 10^{degree}, \"C\")", parse = TRUE) +
  annotate("text", x = 600, y = 0.82,
    label = "paste(\"Susceptible biotype: Depth 3 cm, Temperature \", 10^{degree}, \"C\")",
    parse = TRUE)

blackgrass.plot3
```


Saving the plot:

```
jpeg("/home/christian/stat/manuscripts/2020/Two-step2/ex2-v3.jpg")
blackgrass.plot3
dev.off()
```

```
## pdf
## 2
```